

MODERNIZING THE SYSTEM OF PREPARING PHYSICAL EDUCATION SPECIALISTS FOR PROFESSIONAL AND CAREER ACTIVITIES BASED ON MODERN APPROACHES

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Abstract: This article highlights the importance of introducing a system that supports long-term professional training and fosters career advancement for highly qualified specialists in the field of sports, especially in the context of current social instability. The continuous growth of athletic achievements increases the demand for professionals with modern thinking and advanced competencies. Enhancing specialists' professional success in line with current requirements has become a pressing task, calling for a new stage of development in the sphere of physical education. In developed countries, the creation of a nationally integrated and modernized model for training personnel in physical education is considered a key priority.

Keywords: career, HARD and SOFT skills, specialist, student, model, intellectualism, profiling, trend, creativity, professional potential.

ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA JISMONIY TARBIYA MUTAXASSISLARINING KASBIY VA KARYERAVIY FAOLIYATGA TAYYORGARLIK TIZIMINI YANGILASH

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada hozirgi davrdagi ijtimoiy va ommaviy beqarorlik sharoitida sport sohasi uchun sifatli mutaxassislar tayyorlashga yo‘naltirilgan, uzoq muddatli va bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshiriladigan tayyorgarlik tizimini shakllantirish zarurati yoritilgan. Unda yuqori malakali mutaxassislarning karyera o‘shirishini qo‘llab-quvvatlovchi tizim joriy etish masalasi ilgari suriladi. Sportdagi natijalar doimiy o‘shirib borayotgan bir paytda, zamonaviy fikrlovchi va ijodiy yondashuvga ega kadrlar yetishmovchiligi yanada sezilmoqda. Kasbiy muvaffaqiyatlarga erishish uchun mavjud ehtiyojlar asosida mutaxassislarning salohiyatini oshirish masalasi kun tartibida turibdi. Bu esa jismoniy tarbiya sohasi rivojini yangi bosqichga olib chiqishni taqozo etadi. Ilg‘or mamlakatlar tajribasida esa kadrlar tayyorlashning milliy va zamonaviy integratsiyalashgan modelini yaratish, shu bilan birga, jismoniy tarbiya yo‘nalishidagi mutaxassislar tayyorgarligi tizimini modernizatsiya qilish dolzarb vazifa sifatida qaralmoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: karyera, HARD va SOFT ko‘nikmalar, mutaxassis, talaba, model, intellektual salohiyat, profillash, tendensiyalar, kreativlik, kasbiy rivojlanish.

МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ ПОДГОТОВКИ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ПО ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ К ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО-КАРЬЕРНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается необходимость внедрения системы, поддерживающей длительную профессиональную подготовку и способствующей карьерному росту высококвалифицированных специалистов в сфере спорта, в условиях современной социальной нестабильности. Постоянный рост спортивных достижений усиливает потребность в кадрах с современным мышлением и высоким уровнем профессионализма. Актуальной задачей становится развитие профессиональных навыков специалистов в соответствии с требованиями времени, что требует вывода физического воспитания на качественно новый уровень. В передовых странах создание национально-интегрированной модели подготовки кадров и модернизация системы подготовки специалистов в области физического воспитания рассматриваются как приоритетные направления.

Ключевые слова: карьера, HARD и SOFT навыки, специалист, студент, модель, интеллектуализм, профилирование, тенденции, креативность, профессиональный потенциал.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, as in other fields, special attention is being paid to deeply studying international experiences in the field of physical education and sports, as well as preparing highly qualified specialists capable of competing on equal terms with developed countries. In particular, research and innovative activities carried out in the education sector are aimed at modernizing education, developing new pedagogical technologies and resources, testing them in practice, and implementing them into the educational process. Recent social surveys conducted among sports organization leaders and specialists show that the demands for physical education and sports specialists to possess high organizational, professional, and career potential are increasing. Prospective specialists need to be formed as individuals capable of making independent decisions and working with high efficiency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Issues of professional and career preparation of students in higher education institutions specializing in physical education and sports have been reflected in the scientific works of several researchers from the competency-based approach perspective. In particular, researchers such as K.D. Yarashev, N.A. Muslimov, S.S. Sharipov, G.S. Nasriddinova, and others have presented important scientific conclusions in this area. Additionally, scholars from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries — S.V. Gusev, M.A. Kuznetsova, V.N. Smirnov, N.V. Andreeva, I.P. Morozova — have proposed various theoretical approaches to the essence, structural features, and formation trends of professional and career issues. Furthermore, researchers such as T.V. Yakovleva and O.V. Kovalenko have analyzed the system of professional development of specialists in the field of physical culture, mechanisms to improve their professional competencies, and support career growth. Their experience has demonstrated the effectiveness of scientific and practical recommendations in this area based on empirical evidence.

Research Results. Information is provided regarding solutions to problems related to planning to ensure future professional competencies of students, the dynamics of indicators related to professional intellect, and the development of students' pedagogical competencies during the educational process. During the research, the dynamics of changes in students' attitudes toward their professional activities were analyzed.

Dynamics of Changes in Students' Attitudes toward Professional Activity in Experimental and Control Groups (n=80)

1-table.

Personal Characteristics	EG ($\pm\sigma$) Start (TB)	EG ($\pm\sigma$) End (TO)	Significance (P)	CG ($\pm\sigma$) Start (TB)	CG ($\pm\sigma$) End (TO)	Significance (P)
Stability of Professional Interest	3.2 \pm 1.8	4.1 \pm 0.8	<0.01	3.1 \pm 1.4	3.9 \pm 0.8	<0.05
Inclination toward Professional Activity	3.2 \pm 0.9	4.0 \pm 0.8	<0.01	2.8 \pm 1.3	3.5 \pm 0.7	>0.05
Professional Interest	7.6 \pm 1.9	8.4 \pm 2.8	<0.05	7.6 \pm 2.5	7.9 \pm 2.1	>0.05
Intellectual Component	7.3 \pm 1.8	8.2 \pm 1.6	<0.05	8.0 \pm 1.8	8.2 \pm 2.4	>0.05
Emotional Component	6.4 \pm 3.3	12.1 \pm 2.8	<0.001	6.5 \pm 2.0	7.1 \pm 2.1	>0.05
Volitional Component	8.4 \pm 3.0	8.3 \pm 0.8	>0.05	3.1 \pm 1.4	3.9 \pm 0.8	<0.05

Notes:

EG – Experimental Group

CG – Control Group
TB – Beginning of Experiment
TO – End of Experiment

During our study, the dynamics of changes in students' attitudes toward professional activity were analyzed in both the experimental and control groups. According to the results, the stability of professional interest in the experimental group was 3.2 at the beginning of the study and improved to 4.1 by the end, while in the control group it was 3.1 at the start and increased to 3.9 at the conclusion of the study. Regarding the inclination toward professional activity, the experimental group showed an increase from 3.2 at the beginning to 4.0 at the end, whereas the control group's score rose from 2.8 initially to 3.5 by the end of the study.

Table 2. Distribution of experimental participants based on the stability of professional interest (%)

Stage	Attitude toward profession	Interest	Sufficiently stable interest	Unstable interest
Experimental	Initial	38.1	48.2	13.1
	Final	45.6	51.8	2.6
Control	Initial	38.0	46.3	15.7
	Final	40.1	48.0	11.9

At the initial stage, stable professional interest was observed in 38.4% of the experimental group participants and 37.0% of the control group. The second group is characterized by insufficient satisfaction with the chosen profession, unclear attitude toward it, uncertainty about career prospects, and insufficient manifestation of cognitive activity in mastering the profession. In the experimental group, students of this category made up 48.3% at the initial stage, while in the control group they accounted for 48%.

Table 3. Overall Physical Fitness Indicators of Experimental and Control Group Participants during the Study, n=40

No.	Control Tests	Beginning of Study	End of Study	t	P
		\bar{X}	σ		
1.	60 m sprint (seconds)	TG: 11.44	1.3	16.4	11.10
		NG: 11.49	1.5		
2.	Pull-ups (repetitions)	TG: 4.82	1.7	14.8	7.42
		NG: 4.75	1.4		
3.	Trunk bends forward (repetitions)	TG: 18.41	2.4	18.5	23.11
		NG: 18.59	2.7		
4.	Standing long jump (cm)	TG: 160.24	3.2	15.9	185.4
		NG: 159.92	3.4		

This program enables the development of physical skills through various sports disciplines, promotes a healthy lifestyle, and enhances students' motivation and interest in sports by using innovative methods.

The integration of modern technologies and digitalization processes allows for the efficient use of financial resources, implementation of virtual training sessions and online lessons, as well as effective management of information resources and strengthening cooperation with external partners. Additionally, by using mobile applications, students and graduate students can quickly and effectively analyze their sports performance based on artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and gamification.

Within the framework of modernizing the educational process, the introduction of rapid communication (feedback) technologies, along with an integrated approach to creative thinking, professional erudition, and economic outcomes, has significantly increased educational effectiveness. According to the research results (see Table 6), positive changes were observed in the physical fitness indicators of participants during the experimental activities. The initial overall physical condition of the experimental and control groups was analyzed, and the changes were compared and evaluated.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the system for training specialists in physical education is being effectively modernized through the comprehensive application of pedagogical and methodological innovations, multi-stage approaches, and modern digital technologies. The introduction of individualized approaches in the educational process, virtual learning platforms, and elements for improving sports techniques has significantly enhanced the practical and professional readiness of students and future specialists. As a result, they have thoroughly mastered modern qualifications in physical education and sports, acquiring the necessary skills to be competitive and successful in their professional activities. At the same time, their leadership potential, creative thinking, and professional communication culture have also developed substantially. These changes confirm that the physical education training system is progressively improving in accordance with socio-economic needs.

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